

A STUDY ON PEOPLE'S HUMANITARIAN SERVICES DURING CRISIS

Dr. K. Veerakumar* & Prof. Buhari Isah**

* Assistant Professor & Head of Business Administration, Nallamuthu Gounder Mahalingam College, Pollachi, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India

** Associate Professor, Department of International Humanitarian Law, Institute of European Roma Studies and Research into Crimes Against Humanity and International Law Belgrade, Serbia

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Abstract:

Humanitarian aid is a fundamental expression of the universal value of solidarity between people and a moral imperative. The study aims to find out the extent of humanitarian services rendered by the people during crisis. The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from humanitarian services rendered by the people during crisis in Coimbatore District. The collected primary data were analyzed using simple percentage analysis, z-test, ANOVA and ranking test. The study founded that majority of humanitarian's goal is to save lives, relieve suffering, and maintain human dignity from any situation.

Key Words: Humanitarian, Service, People, Sector, Flood, Crisis, Health, Kindness, Etc.,

Introduction:

India is facing multiple hazards, including climate-related crisis. Over the past years, the number of crisis has doubled and there has been a huge rise in the number of floods. In India between 2010 to 2020, 30 million people were affected by floods and 4.5 million people were affected by cyclones on an average. India is also affected by a wide range of geophysical hazards such as tsunamis, earthquakes, and landslides.

The socio-economic situation of these other crises including the COVID-19 pandemic are created extreme poverty, tress, mental issues, health challenges, violence, abuse , theft, exploitation of girls and boys, crime, etc., Natural disasters lead to food and water shortages and polluted air, with related impacts on children's health, and flooding can destroy all the health and wealth of the people. While the Government has a strong capacity for immediate response, humanitarian assistance remains essential to strengthening systems for mitigating, preparing for and responding to emergencies.

Humanitarians promote welfare ideas to the people, they help to aid by giving money or necessities for those who needed in the society. They provide food, water, clothing, shelter, money, groceries, equipment, or medical supplies which give relief to people during crisis. An act of kindness in someone's heart motivates them to participate in social activities. Humanitarian act includes donating money to a charity and kindness not be measured by how much time or money is spent. During crisis they took care of person about someone they don't personally know.

Objectives of Humanitarian Services:

- The objectives of humanitarian services are to save lives, alleviate suffering and maintain human dignity during and in the aftermath of man-made crises and natural disasters, as well as to prevent and strengthen preparedness for the occurrence of such situations.
- Humanitarian services should be guided by the humanitarian principles of humanity, meaning the centrality of saving human lives and alleviating suffering wherever it is found; impartiality, meaning the implementation of services solely on the basis of need, without discrimination between or within affected populations; neutrality, meaning that humanitarian services must not favour any side in an armed conflict or other dispute where such services is carried out.
- Humanitarian services includes the protection of civilians and those no longer taking part in hostilities, and the provision of food, water and sanitation, shelter, health services and other items of assistance, undertaken for the benefit of affected people and to facilitate the return to normal lives and livelihoods.

Reviews of Literature:

Mooney (2005) observed that particular problems of specific groups at risk would often be the best way to ensure that the group can access the same protection as others. Thus, "addressing the specific problems encountered by IDPs does not preclude protection and assisting other at-risk groups; it simply means that the particular needs and vulnerabilities of IDPs are taken into account and addressed, whether through general or targeted programming"

Collinson (2009) observed that "there needs to be better understanding of the specific group-based protection needs of IDPs, as a separate issue from their material needs and more must be done to ensure that the specific protection needs of internally displaced populations are effectively assessed, monitored and responded to".

Niland (2015) stated that protection clusters play a crucial role in supporting humanitarian actors to develop protection strategies, including to mainstream protection throughout all sectors and to coordinate specialized protection services for affected populations. “Violations of 28 international human rights and humanitarian law, and pre-existing threats and vulnerabilities, may be amongst the principal causes and consequences of humanitarian crises”

Objectives of the Study:

- To study the present humanitarian services during crisis in India.
- To find out the extent of humanitarian services rendered by the people during crisis.

Limitations:

- All the limitations of primary data are applicable to this study.
- The result of the study is based upon the views expressed by the humanitarian services rendered by the people during crisis
- The statistical tools used to analyse the data have their own limitations.

Research Methodology:

Area of the Study:

The research study was done in Coimbatore District.

Nature and Source of Data:

The study is based on both primary and secondary data. Primary data has been collected from humanitarian services rendered by the people during crisis in Coimbatore District by questionnaire method; secondary data have been collected from related journals, websites, magazines and textbooks.

Statistical Tools Used for the Study:

- Simple percentage analysis
- Z-test
- ANOVA
- Ranking Test

Sampling Used:

A sample of 100 people were selected from Coimbatore District by purposive sampling method.

Analysis and Interpretation:

Simple Percentage Analysis:

Table 1: Demographic Profile of the People

Factors	Number of People N=200	Percentage
Gender		
Male	106	53
Female	94	47
Age (Years)		
Up to 25	34	17
26 to 50	108	54
Above 50	58	29
Educational Qualification		
Up to School Level	116	58
Graduate	42	21
Post Graduate	42	21
Annual Income		
Up to Rs.1,00,000	48	24
Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	68	34
Above Rs.2,50,000	84	42
Occupation		
Business	54	27
Employees	108	54
Others	38	19
Type of Family		
Nuclear Family	92	46
Joint Family	108	54

Table 1 describes the demographic profile of the public sector banks customer for the study. Out of 200 people who were taken for the study: it has been identified that most 106 respondent are male, 108 whose age group is under 26 to 50 years, most 116 of the people are graduates, the Annual income of 84 people is above Rs.2,50,000, 108 people are employees and 108 people belong to nuclear family .

Table 2: Z test between Gender, Type of Family and Humanitarian Services

		N	Std. Deviation	Mean	Z	Sig.
Humanitarian Services	Male	106	4.64	21.52	0.237	0.071
	Female	94	4.24	21.83		
	Nuclear Family	92	3.54	19.12		0.071
	Joint Family	108	3.24	19.53		

Table 2, it is understood that the calculated value is greater than 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that gender and type of family have same humanitarian services.

ANOVA:

Table 3: Relationship between age and Humanitarian Services

	Age (Yrs)	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig
Humanitarian Services	Up to 25	34	22.7857	4.04168	0.843	0.777
	26 to 50	108	23.5161	4.88905		
	Above 50	58	20.0870	3.62959		

From the Table 3, it is understood that the calculated values were greater than the 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that, on an average, employees respondents of different age group have the same Humanitarian Services.

Table 4: Relationship between Annual Income and Humanitarian Services

	Annual Income	N	Mean	S.D	Z	Sig
Humanitarian Services	Up to Rs.1,00,000	48	23.785	4.048	0.543	0.777
	Rs.1,00,001 to Rs.2,50,000	68	24.511	4.805		
	Above Rs.2,50,000	84	18.080	3.659		

From the Table 4, it is understood that the calculated values were greater than the 5% level of significance and the null hypothesis is rejected. It is inferred that, on an average, employees respondents of different income group have the different Humanitarian Services.

Ranking Test:

Table 5: People's Humanitarian Services -Ranking Test

Services	Total Score	Rank
Donating food , water, clothes, groceries	658	II
Hygiene kits for those in high risk areas	614	IV
Supporting people with disabilities	587	V
Providing transport in lockdown	560	VI
Getting money to families for basic necessities	638	III
Providing emergency assistance	696	I

The above table shows that people's humanitarian services during crisis. First service was providing emergency assistance to people who need of it, Donating food, water, clothes, groceries was ranked as the second service; Getting money to families for basic necessities was ranked as third service; Hygiene kits for those in high risk areas was ranked as fourth service, Supporting people with disabilities scored the fifth position and Providing transport in lockdown scored the sixth position.

Conclusion:

Human behaviour has undergone a tremendous changes in the recent years. World Humanitarian Day (WHD) is held every year on 19 August to dedicate tribute to aid workers who risk their lives in humanitarian service, and to rally protect people who affected by crises around the world. World leaders have the power to keep the protection of the millions of people caught in crisis around the globe. In India millions of people need humanitarian aid s due to war, violence, natural disasters like flood, tsunami, landslide, Covid 19 pandemic , etc., The study concluded that humanitarian activities includes providing food aid, shelter, education, healthcare or protection. The study founded that majority of humanitarian's goal is to save lives, relieve suffering, and maintain human dignity from any situation.

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